

**ПРАКТИКА ФІТОТЕРАПІЇ У ПІВДЕННО-СХІДНОМУ
МАРОККО (ТАФІЛАЛЕ)**

**PRACTICE OF PHYTOTHERAPY IN SOUTH-EASTERN
MOROCCO (TAFILALET)**

**Толбі Ель Мехді, Ладід Анас
El Mehdi Tolbi, Anas Ladid**

Науковий керівник:

**канд. фарм. наук, доцент, Сениук Ігор Валерійович,
Національний фармацевтичний університет, кафедра біологічної хімії**

Scientific supervisor:

**PhD Pharmaceutical Sciences, Associate Professor, Seniuk Igor
National University of Pharmacy, Department of Biological Chemistry**

orcid: 0000-0003-3819-7331

citochrom@gmail.com

An ethnobotanical pre-survey has provided important information on the place of phytotherapy in the traditional medicine of the oases of south-eastern Morocco, particularly in Tafilalet [1]. The region remains a national center of excellence in this field. Empirical knowledge has been transmitted verbally through generations and has been enriched thanks to a strategic geographical location between North Africa, the Sahara and the Sahel (Al Hasan Al Wazzan dit Léon l'Africain, 16th century). This enrichment is also linked to historical events and the mixing of Amazigh (Berber), Jewish, Saharan and Arab-Muslim civilisations in these oases [2, 3].

This heritage, as for other regions in Morocco, has as its backbone the Amazigh and Arab-Muslim knowledge that has long aroused the curiosity of Moroccan and Arab ethnobotanists [2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

The biological spectrum of the oases of south-eastern Morocco is very marked by its Saharan feature and includes Therophytes (50.80%), Hemicryptophytes (20.75%), Chamaephytes (14.90%), Phanerophytes (11.96%) and Geophytes (1.59%) (Rejdali, 1999). Of the 54 families recorded in the area, 7 account for 60% of the total flora (218 species), the richest being the Asteraceae (17.80%), Poaceae (8.78%), Brassicaceae (11.17%), Fabaceae (7.45%), Caryophyllaceae (5.05%), Chenopodiaceae (3.99%) and Borriginaceae (3.72%) [1, 7].

The old tradition of using plants in traditional medicine in Tafilalet is deeply linked to the isolation of the region, the low purchasing power of families and an already insufficient health service (1 doctor for 10,897 inhabitants and 1 bed for 818 inhabitants [8]). This may explain the liveliness of the traditional health and welfare system, which is really embedded in the socio-cultural context.

The superiority of Western medicine in certain areas does not rule out the fact that 80% of the world's population benefits from the contributions of traditional medicine. Recognising the empirical knowledge of our ancestors as a medicine in its own right and working to bring "Northern" technologies to it can only contribute to its improvement.

The conservation and entry of this heritage and the integration of galenic preparations into the therapeutic arsenal of our country is imperatively linked to their quality and harmlessness criteria as is the case with chemical or biological products [9].

The inventory of this local empirical knowledge, which has stood the test of time and which we are trying to revitalise and preserve, was carried out in collaboration with healers, herbalists and the local population. It is extremely useful because it is in danger of disappearing due to changing lifestyles and communication patterns [3].

This work is a monographic study of medicinal plants and a description of the ways in which they are used in phytotherapy by the local population. Implicitly, one of the socio-economic benefits is the development of the local pharmacopoeia and the development of natural resources in the environment of the oases of Tafilalet. The practice of phytotherapy was approached and its place in the health care system was determined pragmatically without cultural presuppositions.

The data for this ethnobotanical survey have been collected since 1996. The questionnaire was adapted to local conditions and to the increasing complexity of the information as the survey progressed, using a method that collected statements about the locality, the informant-investigator, the practitioners of herbal medicine, the diseases treated and the plants used [1].

The identification and botanical description of the plants was followed in the field and in the laboratory [10, 11, 12]. Specimens of medicinal plants are deposited at the Scientific Institute in Rabat (Morocco).

The database developed (available in the laboratory) allows the establishment of a monograph of plants used in phytotherapy, the synthesis of data, the search for coherence of botanical order and use. It provides a list of diseases (pathologies) known to traditional practitioners and herbalists and a list of plants, including the remarkable ones, used. It also allows to establish with precision the local vernacular names, the scientific names of the genera, species and families of medicinal plants, their main parts used and their modes and forms of administration as well as the supposed and/or observed effects.

The therapeutics followed rely mainly on the properties of food and medicinal plants, divine blessing and grace, and the will of traditional practitioners and healers according to their reputation.

From a dietetic point of view, people choose their diets based on the popular classification of foods as hot, cold, bitter, acidic... Plants are then chosen according to this classification and according to the effect they have. The use of medicinal plants is much more complicated as it follows a logic dictated by different overlapping beliefs and knowledge.

Plant drugs generally fall into two categories: Plants universally known in their botanical, phytochemical and pharmacological properties and which appear for the most part in the Moroccan pharmacopoeia and those of certain industrialised countries;

Unknown or partially known plants for which new investigations are still necessary before their recommendation for use in modern therapeutics.

This ethnobotanical study revealed the importance of the practice of phytotherapy by the isolated and deprived population of Tafilalet. The collection, synthesis and confrontation of the data collected contributed to the transformation of

popular knowledge from oral to written form by establishing a monograph of medicinal plants and their uses.

The computerisation of the collections in the form of a database is a means of putting this knowledge to the test, for a better description, valorisation and preservation of the local pharmacopoeia in a pragmatic way.

This has also made it possible to identify and verify discrepancies in information and thus to highlight confusion in the identity of plants, in their mode of use and in the practice of traditional medicine.

The population of the oases of Tafilalet and the surrounding area seems to use plants for their virtues in about 1952 popular uses or diseases. The choice of the type of preparation and the mode of administration seems to follow the logic of the galenic system. In general, preparations are in liquid, solid, mixture or fumigation form. Ingestion is the most common mode of administration.

The consistency of use in traditional medicine of 215 plant species has been established. These species belong to 46 botanical families.

A study on the coherence between phytochemistry and popular uses is underway.

A valorization in the fields of pharmacology and industry would be a way to ensure the transition from traditional medicine to modern medicine, for a renewed pharmacopoeia. This should be done with greater homogeneity, greater effectiveness and less toxicity. This should not aim at uprooting, but at enhancing and promoting this cultural heritage, which will ultimately enhance biodiversity and contribute to the development and well-being of the local population.

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